

Green synthesis of 1, 2-dihydroquinazolinones and their cytotoxicity

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Abstract:

A simple, efficient and eco-friendly method for the synthesis of quinazolinones has been developed using water as solvent. This protocol involves one pot reaction of readily available substituted isatins and 2-aminobenzamide with montmorillonite-K-10 as a green and eco-friendly catalyst. This method is carried out in shorter reaction time with operational simplicity, higher yields and selectivity. Using this method, a series of sixteen compounds were designed, synthesized and evaluated for their cytotoxicity against human cancer cell lines, such as A549 (lung cancer), DU-145 (prostate cancer), HeLa (cervical cancer) and MCF-7 (breast cancer). All the compounds exhibited considerable antiproliferative activity. Among them, compounds 3a and 3n exhibited significant antiproliferative activity against DU-145 cells with IC₅₀ values 2.86 and 1.98 μ M respectively.

Keyword:

Cytotoxicity, Green synthesis, Clay, Quinazolinones.

Introduction:

Quinazolinone derivatives are important bioactive nitrogen-containing heterocycles and are present in several natural products such as vitamins, alkaloids, etc. Due to their diverse pharmacological and biological activities [1], quinazolinone scaffolds are very important in the synthesis of various biologically active compounds. Recently, these compounds are reported to exhibit as gene associated peptide and vasopressin receptor antagonists [2, 3]. Febrifugine (III), a quinazolinone alkaloid was first isolated from the Chinese herb *Dichoria febrifuga*. It has important biological properties such as antimalarial [4], anticancer [5] and anti-inflammatory [6, 7]. Albacanzole (I) in which the quinazolinone ring is fused by triazole moiety and exhibits broad spectrum anti-fungal activity [8, 11]. DPC-961 (IV), DPC-963 (V) and SM-15811 (VI) (Fig. 1) are compounds having quinazolinone ring and are

known to exhibit 2nd generation HIV activity, ion exchanger properties and also used to treat heart diseases. Considering the importance of quinazolinones from an application perspective, some synthetic methods have been developed. Generally, metal catalysed reductive cyclization of o-nitrobenzamides and ketones or aldehydes [12]. Alternative approaches [13, 14] used anthranilic acid and carboxylic acids or acyl chlorides, anthranilamide and ketone, cyclization of o-amino benzonitrile with ketone for the synthesis of substituted quinazolinones. However, the drawbacks of the previous methods are associated with reaction time and conditions, usage of solvents and outputs of the product yields. So, the development of sustainable alternative method for the synthesis of quinazolinones to environmental issues was highly desirable.

I. Albaconzole, II. (E)-Bogorin, III. Febbrifugine, IV. DPC961, V. DPC083, VI. (+) SM-15811

Fig. 1: Biologically important quinazolinones

Clay is a versatile catalyst having Lewis acid property [15, 18] and is reported to catalyze many important organic reactions [19] such as aldol, Mannich, Michael and Diels–Alder reaction. It is an excellent promoter for the copper-catalyzed coupling reactions. From an environmental and economic perspective, montmorillonite-K-10 has several advantages of being metal ion free, easy to handle, experimental simplicity, cost-effective, non-corrosive and has excellent solubility in water and organic solvents. It has been widely used in Multicomponent reactions under solvent free conditions [20]. In this procedure reaction solvent is water and catalyst is cost effective and non hazardous [21], it is the green principle for synthetic organic chemistry. Due to this, the present protocol was most beneficial while comparing with previously reported methods, it is the noteworthy route for the developing of quinazolinone derivatives via one pot reaction by involving isatin and 2-amino benzimide.

Results and discussion :

1. Chemistry:

Scheme 1: Synthesis of 1,2-dihydroquinazolinones

1.1 Reagents and conditions :

1) 2-aminobenzamide, 2) substituted Isatin, Catalyst, Water, reflux, 3) Product.

The reaction optimization conditions to develop the quinazolinone derivatives by using montmorillonite catalyst are found to be the best. Initially the reaction was kept using 2-aminobenzamide and isatin without any catalyst at atmospheric temperature (entry 1, Table 1), in the presence of universal solvent until 6 h, here the reaction was not proceed, confirmed by the TLC monitoring. Then the reaction was

carried out in the presence of montmorillonite catalyst at the same temperature, product was observed with low yield (entries 6,7). Then the reaction was performed in the reflux condition with catalyst (entries 2-5 & 8-10, Table 1), finally offered the required product in the good to excellent yields in the water medium.

Table 1: Optimization of various solvents at different temperatures for the synthesis of 1, 2-dihydroquinazolinones

Entry	Solvent	Temperature (°C)	Catalystb	Time (hr)	Yielda (%)
1	water	Rt	--	6	--
2	water	Reflux	--	4	<10
3	ethanol	40	--	5	15
4	methanol	40	--	5	10
5	hexane	50	Clay	5	10
6	water	Rt	Clay	6	20
7	ethanol	Rt	Clay	4	30
8	methanol	40	Clay	4	70
9	ethanol	60	Clay	4	80
10	water	100	Clay	3-4	87

Then the reaction was carried out using various concentrations of the catalyst such as 2, 5, 10 and 15 mol % in the 3-6 h time period (Table 2). 2 and 5 mol % of catalyst gives only 52 and 60 % of the required product and if the catalyst concentration is increased more than 10 mol % there is no variations in the yield of the product. The presence of an electron withdrawing group at position 5 of the isatin slowed down the reaction resulting in a comparable increase in the reaction time and lower yields. It is important to note that under the conditions mentioned above, the quinazolinone was formed as an exclusive desired product employing montmorillonite-K-10 as the catalyst. With the optimized conditions a series of compounds (Table 3) were synthesized and evaluated for their anti-microbial activity.

Table 2 : Condensation of isatin and 2-aminobenzamide in water at different concentrations of clay

Entry	Catalyst (mole %)	Time (h)	Yield(%)a
1	-	6	Nil
2	2	5	52
3	5	5	60
4	10	3.5	87
5	15	5	87

Table 3: Synthesis of 1, 2-dihydroquinazolinones derivatives

Entry	2-Aminobenzimide	Isatin	Product (1a-16a)	Time (h)	Yield %
1		3	87		
2		3	80		
3		3	79		
4		3	77		
5		3	80		
6		3	85		
7		4	84		

1.2 Plausible mechanism :

Fig. 2 : Plausible mechanism for the formation of Quinazolinone

The plausible mechanism for the formation of quinazolinone ring from isatin and 2-aminobenzamide is outlined in Fig. 2. The reaction is hypothetical to proceed with the formation of a keto imine from 2-aminobenzamide with isatin. Hence, this step was promoted by the catalyst montmorillonite-K-10 and it reacted with the keto group to form an imino derivative with the elimination of water. The imine carbon which is active for a nucleophilic attack was then attacked by the adjacent nitrogen atom to cyclise into a conformationally constructive six membered ring to form the desired product.

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Biological Studies :

1.3 Cytotoxic activity :

Table 1: Cytotoxicity evaluation for compounds in selected human cancer cell lines.

Compound	IC50 values (in μM)a			
	HeLab	A549c	MCF-7d	DU-145e
3a	3.32	2.76	3.18	2.86
3b	5.91	6.98	5.98	8.56
3c	2.98	4.24	3.22	4.26
3d	12.8	11.7	13.4	11.8
3e	5.72	8.12	9.89	3.86
3f	7.49	9.19	10.8	13.4
3g	12.9	11.1	10.4	16.5
3h	8.09	5.96	8.53	8.93
3i	19.5	13.2	18.7	12.1

3j	11.8	13.2	12.6	3.19
3k	5.08	9.65	14.6	12.4
3l	5.94	8.05	9.47	13.7
3m	7.17	7.14	6.44	12.0
3n	2.19	2.30	3.78	1.98
3o	7.79	11.4	6.08	6.72
3p	6.05	5.03	4.05	5.86
Etoposide	1.905	2.238	1.633	2.070

To estimate the cytotoxicity of N-acyldihydrophenanthridine derivatives (3a-p), MTT assay was carried out on the selected human cancer cell lines, such as lung cancer (A549), breast cancer (MCF-7), prostate cancer (DU-145) and cervical cancer (HeLa). The cytotoxicity results in comparison to the positive controls like etoposide are expressed in IC₅₀ values and are tabulated in Table 1. The results revealed that all the synthesized compounds 3a-p exhibited moderate to good cytotoxic activities with IC₅₀ values ranging from 1.61-26.05 μ M. Based on the antiproliferative data, the SAR of these spiro benzodiazepines was examined. All the compounds showed pronounced activity against A549 (lung cancer) and DU-145 (prostate cancer) cancer cell lines as compared to other cell lines. The most active derivatives in this series were 3a, 3c, 3e and 3n; interestingly the derivatives 3a, 3c, 3e and 3n were found to be promising derivatives with IC₅₀ values of 1.98 and 2.86 μ M, respectively, against DU-145 cell line.

Experimental Section:

1.4 Cytotoxicity evaluation :

The cytotoxicity of these N-acyldihydrophenanthridine derivatives was determined using MTT assay.²² Cancer cells (DU-145, MCF-7, HeLa and A549) were used in this assay. 1×10^4 cells/well were seeded in 200 μ l Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium (DMEM), supplemented with 10% FBS in each well of 96-well microculture plates and incubated for 24 h at 37 °C in a CO₂ incubator. All the derivatives diluted to the desired concentrations (500 nM, 1 μ M, 5 μ M, 10 μ M, 25 μ M, 50 μ M, 75 μ M, 100 μ M and 150 μ M) in culture medium, were added to the wells with respective vehicle control. Doxorubicin and etoposide treated cells in the same concentration range were used as standards. After 48 h of incubation, 10 μ l MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazoliumbromide) (5 mg/ml) was added to each well and the plates were further incubated for 4 h. Then the supernatant from each well was carefully removed, formosan crystals were dissolved in 100 μ l of DMSO and absorbance at 570 nm wavelength was recorded at a wavelength of 540 nm using an ELx800 microplate reader (BioTek, USA).

Materials and Methods:

All chemicals, reagents were purchased from the commercial sources and were used without further purification. Reactions were monitored by TLC on silica gel glass plate containing 60 GF-254, and visualization was done by UV light and iodine vapour. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker UXNMR/XWIN-NMR (300 MHz) or Innova Varian-VXR-unity (400 MHz) instruments. Chemical shifts were expressed in parts per million (in ppm) downfield from TMS expressed as internal standard and coupling constants are expressed in Hz. ¹H NMR spectral data were reported in the following order: multiplicity (s, singlet; brs, broad singlet; d, doublet; dd, doublet of doublets; t, triplet; m, multiplet), coupling constants in Hz, and number of protons. ESI mass spectra were recorded on a Micromass Quattro LC using ESI+ software with capillary voltage 3.98 kV and an ESI mode positive ion trap detector. High resolution mass spectra were recorded on a QSTAR XL Hybrid MS-MS mass spectrometer. Melting points were determined with an electro thermal digital melting point apparatus IA9100 and are uncorrected.

General reaction procedure for the preparation of compounds (1a-16a)

All the reactions were performed using the following procedure. To the solution of 2-aminobenzamide (1 mmol) in water add substituted isatin (1 mmol) and montmorillonite-K-10 (10 mol %), reflux the reaction at 100 °C for 4 h, appearance of solid indicates the product formation and which was also monitored by the TLC. Then filter the reaction mixture and recrystallize the resulted solid to obtain the respective pure quinazolinones in good to excellent yields.

1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3a)

Dirty white powder; 87 % yield; mp 290-295 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 9.76 (s, 1H), 7.80 (d, J = Hz, 1H), 7.59 (d, J=Hz, 1H), 7.29-7.21 (m, 2H), 7.03 (t, 2H), 6.85 (d, 1H), 6.76 (t, 1H), 6.67 (d, 1H), 6.15 (bs, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 70.84, 109.96, 113.77, 114.07, 117.05, 121.93, 124.94, 126.73, 129.18, 130.38, 132.98, 141.88, 146.53, 164.14, 175.79; IR (KBr pellets) ν : 3363, 3339, 3179, 3050, 1730, 1706, 1663, 1620, 1509, 1483, 1470, 1359, 1324, 1185, 748 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS : m/z = 266 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₂O₂N₃ calculated m/z: 266.09240, found m/z: 266.09225 (M+H)⁺.

5-chloro-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3b)

White powder; 80 % yield; mp 289-294 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 7.86 (s,1H), 7.56- 7.49 (m, 3H), 6.81-6.62 (m, 4H) 4.79 (s, 1H), 3.82 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 70.02, 119.70, 112.67, 112.83, 112.94, 115.80, 117.40, 126.80, 130.43, 133.09, 137.63, 146.14, 164.10, 175.80; IR (KBr pellets) ν : 3252, 1731, 1660, 1651, 1613, 1514, 1504, 1483, 1440, 1359, 1268, 1190, 753, 694 cm⁻¹;ESI-MS: m/z = 300 (M+H)⁺; HRMS

(ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₁O₂N₃Cl calculated m/z: 300.05343, found m/z: 300.05341 (M+H)⁺.

5-fluoro-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3c)

White powder; 79 % yield; mp 285-287 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 9.98(s, 1H), 7.78 (m, 2H), 7.23 (bs, 2H), 7.01 (t, J = 7.36 Hz, 1H), 6.81-6.66 (m, 3H), 6.58 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 71.12, 110.70, 112.67, 113.83, 113.94, 116.80, 117.40, 126.80, 130.43, 133.09, 137.63, 146.14, 164.10, 175.80; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3282, 1741, 1661, 1632, 1613, 1520, 1185, 1146, 1124, 1042, 817, 758, 710, 693, 636, 616 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 284 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₁O₂N₃F calculated m/z: 284.08298, found m/z: 284.08315 (M+H)⁺.

5-bromo-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3d)

Light red powder; 77 % yield; mp 280-285 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 6.43 (s, 1H), 6.68 (d, J = 7.93 Hz, 1H), 6.74-6.78 (m, 2H), 7.24 (dt, J = 1.51 & 8.30 Hz, 1H), 7.40 (dd, J = 1.88 & 8.30 Hz, 1H), 7.48-7.51 (m, 1H), 7.61 (d, J = 1.70 Hz, 1H), 7.79 (d, J = 7.55 Hz, 1H), 10.02 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 70.83, 111.67, 113.74, 113.88, 117.32, 126.74, 127.81, 131.17, 132.89, 133.01, 140.91, 146.04, 163.92, 175.28; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 1731, 1660, 1614, 1513, 1482, 1434, 1358, 1302, 1268, 1189, 1145, 1122, 817, 752, 628, 566, 538 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 343 (M)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₁O₂N₃Br calculated m/z: 343.00292, found m/z: 343.00306 (M)⁺.

5-iodo-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3e)

White powder ; 80 % yield; mp 240-245 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): 10.04 (s, 1H), 7.77 (d, J = 8.6 Hz, 3H), 7.58 (d, J = 7.9 Hz, 1H), 7.25 (t, J = 7.55 Hz, 1H), 6.76-6.64 (m, 4H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 70.76, 83.96, 112.42, 113.84, 117.82, 127.05, 130.99, 133.28, 133.55, 139.09, 141.31, 145.72, 164.18, 175.02; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3282, 1741, 1661, 1613, 1520, 1484, 1425, 1371, 1335, 1299, 1265, 1185, 1146, 1124, 1042, 817, 758, 636, 616 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 390 (M)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₀O₂N₃I calculated m/z: 390.90292, found m/z: 390.90306 (M)⁺.

5-methyl-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3f)

White powder; 85 % yield; mp 150-155 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 2.30 (s, 3H), 6.49 (s, 1H), 6.65-6.80 (m, 3H), 7.07 (d, J = 7.55 Hz, 1H), 7.22 (t, J = 8.30 & 15.29 Hz, 1H), 7.34 (s, 1H), 7.40 (brs, 1H), 7.75 (d, J = 7.17 Hz, 1H), 9.81 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 20.48, 70.92, 109.73, 113.72, 113.97, 117.06, 125.49, 126.75, 129.00, 130.62, 131.16, 132.94, 139.20, 146.40, 164.19, 175.77; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3314, 2922, 2853, 1706, 1655, 1613, 1513, 1489, 1357, 1329, 1270, 1207, 1154, 811, 751, 698 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 280 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₆H₁₄O₂N₃ calculated m/z: 280.10805, found m/z: 280.10812 (M+H)⁺.

5-nitro-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3g)

White powder; 84% yield; mp 230-235 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 6.67 (d, J = 7.93 Hz, 1H), 6.75 (t, J = 7.55 & 14.91 Hz, 1H), 7.00 (d, J = 8.68 Hz, 1H), 7.14 (s, 1H), 7.24 (t, J = 8.49 & 16.61 Hz, 1H), 7.71 (d, J = 7.17 Hz, 1H), 8.19-8.40 (m, 3H), 10.85 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 70.56, 109.99, 113.90, 117.62, 120.62, 126.81, 127.10, 130.02, 133.19, 142.41, 145.90, 148.22, 163.82, 176.04; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3342, 3021, 2860, 1727, 1649, 1616, 1522, 1482, 1405, 1339, 1296, 1252, 1229, 1189, 1143, 1121, 1085, 837, 746, 733, 690, 635, 550 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 311 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₁O₄N₄ calculated m/z: 311.07748, found m/z: 311.07744 (M+H)⁺.

1-benzyl-5-chloro-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4(3H)-dione (3h)

White powder; 79 % yield; mp 150-155 °C; ¹H NMR (DMSO-d₆, 300 MHz) δ: 8.1 (s, 1H), 7.8 (d, 1H), 7.6 (s, 1H), 7.55 (t, 2H, J = 8.1 Hz), 6.9 (s, 1H), 6.77-6.68 (m, 4H), 6.5 (bs, 1H), 6.0 (bs, 1H), 4.9 (s, 1H), 4.8 (s, 2H), 3.8 (d, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 145.16, 141.26, 133.8, 133.4, 130.75, 129.4, 126.09, 123.8, 121.6, 116.4, 115.41, 113.70, 107.65, 69.27, 41.89; IR (KBr pellets, ν: 3758, 3713, 3707, 3685, 3644, 3625, 3583, 3270, 2923, 2357, 1737, 1731, 1715, 1666, 1660, 1650, 1644, 1633, 1613, 1514, 1504, 1494, 1485, 1434, 1336 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS m/z: 389 (M+); HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₂₂H₁₆ClN₃O₂ calculated m/z: 389.08298, found m/z: 389.08315 (M+H)⁺.

5-methoxy-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3i)

White powder; 85 % yield; mp 270-275 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 9.74 (s, 1H), 7.79 (d, 1H), 7.5 (s, 1H), 7.45 (bs, 1H), 7.1 (s, 1H), 6.81-6.45 (m, 4H), 6.45 (s, 1H), 3.75 (s, 3H); ¹³C NMR (60 MHz, DMSO), ppm, 174.8, 163, 154.17, 145.58, 134.01, 131.94, 129.27, 125.71, 116.01, 144.44, 112.76, 110.43, 109.45, 70.23, 54.36; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3314, 3215, 2924, 1719, 1648, 1609, 1513, 1485, 1440, 1357, 1296, 1270, 1234, 1162, 1043, 1024, 824, 794, 756, 715, 698, 672, 621, 578 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 296 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₂O₂N₃ calculated m/z: 296.09240, found m/z: 296.09225 (M+H)⁺.

5,6-dimethyl-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3j)

White powder; 87 % yield; mp 320-325 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 2.39 (d, 6H), 6.49 (s, 1H), 6.65-6.80 (m, 3H), 7.07 (d, J = 7.55 Hz, 1H), 7.22 (t, J = 8.30 & 15.29 Hz, 1H), 7.34 (s, 1H), 7.40 (brs, 1H), 7.75 (d, J = 7.17 Hz, 1H), 9.81 (s, 1H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 20.48, 70.92, 109.73, 113.72, 113.97, 117.06, 125.49, 126.75, 129.00, 130.62, 131.16, 132.94, 139.20, 146.40, 164.19, 175.77; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3311, 3301, 2902, 2833, 1706, 1685, 1623, 1513, 1489, 1357, 1329, 1270, 1207, 1154, 811, 751, 698 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 293 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₇H₁₅O₂N₃ calculated m/z: 293.09240, found m/z: 293.133 (M+H)⁺.

1-benzyl-1'H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3k)

White powder; 82 % yield; mp 240-245 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 8.04 (s, 1H), 7.79 (d, 1H), 7.68 (s, 1H), 7.59 (d, 1H), 7.12 (t, 1H), 6.93-6.84 (m, 3H), 6.77-6.68 (m, 5H), 5.94 (s, 2H), 4.72 (s, 2H). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 170.02, 163.28, 145.15, 141.29, 133.88, 132.04, 129.40, 129.4, 127.23, 126.09, 123.08, 121.31, 116.41, 113.86, 112.85, 107.38, 69.62, 41.89; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3329, 3179, 3054, 2918, 1705, 1667, 1615, 1511, 1489, 1466, 1454, 1362, 1314, 1264, 1175, 1142, 993, 749, 696, 678, 630 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 356 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₂O₂N₃ calculated m/z: 356.09240, found m/z: 356.09225 (M+H)⁺.

1-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-ylmethyl)-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]2,4(3H)-dione (3l)

White powder; 84 % yield; mp 260-265 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 8.01 (s, 1H), 7.79 (d, 1H), 7.77 (s, 1H), 7.66 (d, J = 7.21 Hz, 1H), 7.59 (d, J = 7.26 Hz, 1H), 7.29-6.75 (m, 7H), 5.94 (s, 2H), 4.72 (s, 2H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 42.67, 70.67, 100.57, 107.41, 107.80, 109.16, 113.84, 114.05, 117.31, 120.31, 122.64, 124.75, 126.79, 128.64, 130.38, 133.03, 142.27, 146.28, 146.47, 147.44, 164.22, 174.05; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3193, 3059, 1658, 1670, 1615, 1487, 1467, 1444, 1356, 1272, 1244, 1190, 1174, 1143, 1100, 1036, 743, 695 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 400 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₂₃H₁₈O₄N₃ calculated m/z: 400.12918, found m/z: 400.12982 (M+H)⁺.

1-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-ylmethyl)-5-chloro-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]2,4(3H)-dione (3m)

White powder; 77% yield; mp 195-200 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 3.62 (s, 3H), (bs, 1H), 7.55 (bs, 1H), 7.4 (bs, 1H), 7.41-6.79 (m, 4H), 6.54 (s, 1H), 5.96 (s, 2H) 4.89 (s, 2H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 46.7, 70.67, 103.57, 106.41, 107.80, 109.16, 113.84, 114.05, 117.31, 119.31, 120.64, 124.25, 126.79, 128.64, 130.38, 133.03, 142.27, 146.28, 146.47, 147.44, 164.20; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3270, 1671, 1660, 1650, 1644, 1633, 1613, 1574, 1567, 1556, 1537, 1530, 1514, 1494, 1485, 1471, 1454, 1434, 1416, 1392, 1371, 1336, 1172, 1253, 1123, 1080, 1029, 815, 752 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 434 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₂₃H₁₇O₄N₃Cl calculated m/z: 434.09021, found m/z: 434.09025 (M+H)⁺.

1-(benzo[d][1,3]dioxol-5-ylmethyl)-5-bromo-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]2,4(3H)-dione (3n)

White powder; 76 % yield; mp 160-165 °C; ¹H NMR (DMSO-D₆, 300 MHz, ppm) δ: 7.53, (t, 3H, J = 8.3Hz), 7.3 (bs, 1H), 7.20 (t, 3H, J = 8.3Hz), 6.7 (d, 3H, J = 7.9Hz), 6.62 (t, 2H, J = 7.7Hz), 5.9 (bs, 4H). ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 173.47, 170.80, 163.72, 148.75, 1425.60, 141.74, 134.32, 132.48, 131.20, 129.84, 127.68, 124.24, 122.09, 116.85, 115.85, 113.35, 108.43, 70.07, 42034; IR (KBr pellets, ν: 3411, 2923, 2853, 1731, 1650, 1585, 1546, 1487, 1452, 1402, 1315, 1257, 1151, 743 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS m/z: 433 (M+). HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₂₂H₁₇O₂N₃

calculated m/z: 433.08298, found m/z: 434.08315 (M+H)⁺.

7-fluoro-1H-spiro[indoline-3,2'-quinazoline]-2,4'(3'H)-dione (3o)

light white powder; 79 % yield; mp 310-315 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ, 9.96 (s, 1H), 7.78 (d, 2H, J = 7.5Hz), 7.70 (s, 1H), 7.23 (s, 1H) 7.09, 6.99 (t, 1H, J = 7.36Hz), 6.81-6.78 (m, 2H) 6.68 (s, 1H, J = 7.9Hz) 6.58 (s, 1H) ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 71.12, 110.70, 112.67, 113.83, 113.94, 116.80, 117.40, 126.80, 130.43, 133.09, 137.63, 146.14, 164.10, 175.80 IR (KBr pellets, ν: 3326, 3177, 1732, 1614, 1588, 1516, 1486, 1370, 1358, 1314, 1272, 1254, 1203, 1152, 1083, 1033, 902, 736, 686, 661, 603, 578, 527 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 284 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₅H₁₀O₂N₃F calculated m/z: 284.08298, found m/z: 284.08315 (M+H)⁺.

1'H-spiro[cyclohexane-1,2'-quinazoline]-4'(3'H)-one (3p)

White powder; 86 % yield; mp 235-239 °C; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆) δ 7.80 (s, 1H), 7.25, (s, 1H), 6.85 (d, 2H), 5.24 (s, 1H) 2.77 (bs, 1H), 2.17 (s, 1H), 1.82-1.45 (m, 8H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, DMSO-d₆): δ 21.00, 24.17, 36.95, 67.67, 114.25, 116.85, 127.12, 132.90, 145.95, 163.69; IR (KBr pellets) ν: 3365, 3169, 3023, 2926, 2852, 1647, 1504, 1482, 1416, 1381, 1323, 1268, 1143, 756 cm⁻¹; ESI-MS: m/z = 217 (M+H)⁺; HRMS (ESI) m/z for C₁₃H₁₇O₂N₂ calculated m/z: 217.13354, found m/z: 217.13347 (M+H)⁺.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, a simple, efficient and environmentally benign method for the synthesis of 1, 2-dihydroquinazolinones has been developed by employing montmorillonite-K-10 as a catalyst in water. The advantages of this method include its simplicity of operation, clean reactions, absence of side products and higher yields. Furthermore, these synthesized derivatives were screened for their cytotoxicity among these 3a, 3c, 3e and 3n derivatives exhibited significant cytotoxicity.

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